

eIDPS: A real-time eBPF-based and Machine Learning-powered Network Intrusion Detection and Prevention Solution

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Abstract—As technology evolves rapidly, more and more critical infrastructures are going online. Malicious individuals more often than not try to exploit such infrastructures; thus, cyber-attacks have become a major issue for users and businesses. Current software applications struggle to confront the more sophisticated cyber-attacks that cyber-criminals use. Additionally, network security software applications, which utilize network packets for detecting cyber-attacks, consume a great amount of system resources, such as Central Processing Unit (CPU). This paper proposes a cyber-security software application, named eIDPS, which utilizes minimum system resources and employs novel technologies, such as the Extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF), which can run virtualized functions directly in the kernel, as well as Machine Learning (ML) for analyzing packets, detecting and preventing various network attacks. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that such an implementation has been proposed on a packet-level regarding network intrusion detection and/or prevention. The proposed proof-of-concept method was compared to existing techniques for detecting and/or preventing cyber-attacks and the experiment results demonstrated its validity in terms of speed, efficiency, system resource consumption, attack detection, as well as faster cyber-attack prevention. Furthermore, the findings of this paper underline the necessity to shift focus to more advanced technologies that can not only identify but also prevent cyber-attacks in a shorter period of time and highlight the benefits offered by combining eBPF with ML when designing intrusion detection and prevention solutions.

Index Terms—eBPF, XDP, Neural Network, Network Intrusion Detection System, Security

I. INTRODUCTION

CYBERSECURITY solutions like Network Intrusion Detection Systems (NIDS) and Network Intrusion Prevention Systems (NIPS) have been developed as a result of the serious threat that frequent cyberattacks pose to individuals and corporations [1]–[3]. Additionally, to improve detection accuracy, machine learning (ML) techniques have been used in NIDS and NIPS more frequently [4], [5] as ML models are capable of efficiently analyzing patterns and identifying anomalies due to the high volume of network traffic.

Nonetheless, high traffic volumes, encrypted communication, and sophisticated infrastructure are some of the difficulties in implementing NIDS on large networks. DoS attack detection remains difficult due to scalability and computational limitations. Despite ML advancements, existing solutions often struggle to balance accuracy, performance, and scalability.

An advanced implementation of Berkeley Packet Filtering (BPF) [6], eBPF [7] has become an effective instrument for

packet filtering, network traffic analysis, and system monitoring. eBPF allows programs to function in kernel space, thus enabling efficient real-time packet processing. A significant advancement is eXpress Data Path (XDP) [8], which filters packets at the hardware level using Network Interface Cards (NICs) to significantly improve detection accuracy and response time.

To address the limitations identified in the literature, this paper proposes eIDPS, a proof-of-concept ML-powered Network Intrusion Detection and Prevention solution utilizing eBPF and XDP for real-time packet filtering. Unlike conventional eBPF-based systems focused solely on monitoring, eIDPS integrates an optimized ML model for packet-level intrusion detection and prevention, minimizing resource consumption for scalability. The system is evaluated against existing approaches based on speed, efficiency, resource usage, and attack detection/prevention capabilities.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II discusses related literature work conducted in recent years regarding the use of ML in NIDS and NIPS solutions as well as research studies related to eBPF and XDP and the potential they offer to cyber-security and intrusion detection and/or prevention; Section III refers to the implementation of the proposed proof-of-concept software application, namely eIDPS, that is capable of detecting and preventing malicious packets in real-time; Section IV presents the experiments that were conducted to evaluate the proposed model and compare it with current solutions for cyber-attack detection and/or prevention; Section V summarizes the results of this research and discusses future work directions.

II. STATE OF THE ART

A. Machine Learning in Network Intrusion Detection Systems

Recent advancements in NIDS have leveraged deep learning and machine learning techniques to enhance detection accuracy, yet challenges remain in real-world applicability, dataset relevance, computational efficiency, and generalizability. Xu and Shen [9] developed an NIDS using Deep Neural Networks (DNN) with Gate Recurrent Units (GRU), Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), and SoftMax, achieving high detection rates (99.42% on KDD-99, 99.31% on NSL-KDD). However, its practical application remains unverified, and the use of outdated datasets limits its relevance. Waskle et al. [10] enhanced NIDS with Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Random

Forest (RF), outperforming SVM, Naive Bayes, and Decision Tree with 96.78% accuracy. However, the absence of real-time testing and the reliance on NSL-KDD leave gaps in the evaluation.

Vinayakumar et al. [11] introduced a DNN-based NIDS with host intrusion detection, surpassing traditional ML classifiers in benchmark datasets and real-time scenarios, but with high computational costs. Similarly, Ashiku et al. proposed a deep learning-based NIDS for detecting known and zero-day attacks, achieving 94.4% accuracy on UNSW-NB15, though generalizability and computational efficiency remain concerns. Lastly, Vinayakumar et al. [12] applied CNNs for NIDS, using high-level feature extraction to outperform classical ML classifiers, although training costs scale with model complexity.

B. eBPF security solutions

Current literature suggests that the use of eBPF and XDP significantly enhances packet processing efficiency. According to Jørgensen [13], eBPF/XDP scales CPU utilization dynamically with packet load, reducing CPU usage compared to alternatives such as iptables and DPDK. Caviglione [14] and Vieira et al. [15] also highlighted eBPF's real-time malware detection capabilities.

Wang and Chang [16] demonstrated that integrating eBPF with NIDS improves network throughput while reducing CPU overhead compared to Snort. Bachl [17] combined eBPF with ML, achieving 99% accuracy on CICIDS-2017, though limited by fixed-point arithmetic constraints. Miano et al. [18] applied eBPF/XDP to DDoS mitigation using SmartNICs, while Zhang et al. [19] proposed an eBPF-based flow intrusion detection system with high F1-scores but limitations in real-time processing of persistent flows.

XDP's adaptability was highlighted by Høiland-Jørgensen [13], achieving up to 24M packets/sec on a single core, though kernel bypass alternatives offer trade-offs. Hohlfeld et al. [20] noted that packet offloading can enhance performance if workloads are well-optimized.

Existing solutions focus on either detection or prevention, often lacking real-time capabilities. While ML-based NIDS approaches improve detection, they rarely incorporate proactive filtering. eBPF/XDP enables efficient kernel-level monitoring and filtering, but prior work rarely fully integrates ML. Our approach combines eBPF with XDP and ML for real-time intrusion detection and prevention, addressing resource efficiency, adaptability, and attack mitigation. Unlike previous studies, we evaluate not only detection accuracy but also Input/Output (I/O) metrics, CPU and RAM usage, and effectiveness against diverse threats, offering a comprehensive assessment of our proposed eIDPS solution.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

This chapter refers to the implementation of the proposed proof-of-concept solution, which uses a neural network for the classification of the network packets and benefits from the offloading of the packet processing in the NIC through XDP.

A. Threat model

In this proof-of-concept we defined eIDPS aiming to detect and prevent cyber-attacks to a corporate network. Primary assets under protection are intellectual property and network integrity. Our implementation employs an amalgamation of ML-based anomaly detection with in-kernel packet processing and decision making on a packet level to mitigate threat.

Finally, we consider attackers with the ability to execute sophisticated attacks including packet manipulation, malicious packet injection, and evasion techniques. These attackers can achieve various levels of network access, from remote code execution to total access to the system.

B. Architecture

eIDPS comprises three layers, namely: the Operating System layer, the Kernel layer, and the Data Link layer as can be seen in Figure 1.

The Operating System Layer includes the User Space where the Hook script, Training Module, and training Dataset reside. The Hook script hooks the eBPF program in the kernel while the training Dataset is utilized by the Training Module to train the ML model.

Furthermore, The Kernel Layer (version 6.1.0) includes the eBPF program, which acts as the IDS/IPS (Intrusion Detection/Prevention System) module and comprises the Tracing and Security modules. These modules are responsible for packet analysis and for deciding whether to allow or reject the arrival of IPv4 packets. This decision-making process is guided by the weights and biases derived from the training of the ML model, which are integrated into the Security Module. The Kernel IDS/IPS module is a core component that directly connects the eBPF program's capabilities to the broader goal of packet inspection and decision-making based on machine learning.

Finally, the Data Link Layer contains the NIC driver, through where Network Traffic passes in the system. Inside the NIC's card driver the XDP program resides, which operates along with the Tracing module in order to capture ingress and egress traffic for analysis.

C. Workflow

The proposed solution can be divided into two workflow scenarios. The first one shows the flow of the pre-configuration of the system while the second one presents how the proposed eIDPS solution acts when egress or ingress traffic is captured in the NIC.

The first flow, as depicted in Figure 2, begins at time zero with the pre-processing of the training dataset, which is split and used to train and validate the ML model. The training dataset gets inserted as an input into the Neural Network model that serves as the ML algorithm in the proposed solution. Following, the Hook Script is executed, which compiles and attaches the eBPF program to the kernel. At the same time, the output of the Neural Network, which is the weights and the bias, is inserted into the kernel's IDS/IPS Module. Upon execution of the Hook Script, the eIDPS commences its operational functionality.

Fig. 1: Architecture Diagram

Fig. 2: Pre-configuration workflow

In the diagram presented in Figure 3, the second workflow illustrates how eIDPS functions after being configured and deployed in a system where egress and ingress traffic is captured by the NIC card. As depicted, the internet traffic passes through the NIC card and reaches the Tracing Module, where all incoming packets are processed. Only valid and complete IPv4 packets are permitted to enter the system and are subsequently forwarded to the Security Module. This ensures that incomplete or malformed packets are filtered out, avoiding unnecessary computation.

In the Security Module, the weights and biases are rounded to bypass the floating-point limitation. These adjusted values are then applied to compute the Maliciousness Indication Number (MIN) for each packet. The calculation follows equation (1), as presented in [21], where x represents the packet header. This equation, is a fundamental linear model widely used for its simplicity, computational efficiency, and interpretability.

The linear combination of the weight and the input feature ($x[i]$) allows the system to assign importance to specific packet

attributes, while the bias adjusts the overall decision threshold. The computational cost of this equation is minimal, as it involves a single multiplication and addition for each feature. This efficiency ensures that the Security Module can process packets at high throughput without introducing significant latency, making it ideal for high-speed networks and real-time traffic monitoring. This approach ensures that the processing remains lightweight and suitable for real-time packet analysis, a critical requirement for eIDPS.

$$y = bias + weight * x[i] \quad (1)$$

Finally, the Security Module is responsible for the decision-making regarding dropping a packet or not. If the MIN number is greater than zero (0) then the network packet is classified as malicious and gets dropped, while if it is equal or less than zero (0) then the packet is considered benign and is let through.

Fig. 3: eIDPS workflow

D. ML Model

This section refers to the implementation and training of the ML model, which is part of the solution proposed in this paper, in order to preconfigure the system at time zero as described in the first workflow presented in section III-C.

1) *Dataset pre-processing*: The CICIDS-2017 IDS dataset [22] was selected as it contains 2,830,751 packets of both anomalous and normal traffic, making it suitable for multiclass classification. While the ML model is trained on network flows, it classifies individual packets in real-time. Certain attacks, such as SSH brute force, port scans (e.g., Nmap), and DoS attacks (e.g., Hulk, Slowloris, GoldenEye), exhibit strong correlations between packet byte values and specific packet characteristics. These attacks generate repetitive malicious patterns, high packet rates, or distinct anomalies in headers and payloads, making them identifiable at the packet level despite flow-based training.

The dataset underwent pre-processing, including categorical-to-numeric conversion for the "Label" column, normalization of feature values, and a train-test split with 75% of the data used for training and 25% for testing. A random state function was applied to shuffle the data before splitting.

2) *NN configuration*: A sequential NN model was created, with the input layer accommodating the number of processed features from the dataset. Feature importance was determined based on the mean absolute weights of input connections, following the methodology in [23]. Features with a threshold below 0.1 were removed, reducing the feature set. The hidden layer configured with 56 neurons with a Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function, and an Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.0001 was used for training. To prevent overfitting, a dropout layer was included. The model was trained for 100 epochs with a batch size of 500.

IV. EVALUATION

The evaluation of the proposed solution involved three scenarios using the CICIDS2017 dataset. The first scenario used Snort, a user-space NIDS/NIPS; the second utilized Bachl’s eBPF-based solution [17] with a Decision Tree (DT); and the third tested the proposed eIDPS solution, combining eBPF, XDP, and an ML model for real-time detection and prevention.

The testbed consisted of an Intel i7-3770 processor, 32 GB RAM, a 500 GB SSD, and a NetLink BCM57781 Ethernet card supporting XDP and eBPF. Two Kali Linux VMs, each with 2 virtual cores and 8 GB RAM, were connected via an internal network to isolate traffic. Attack traffic was generated using tools like hping3 and Metasploit to simulate six attacks: SYN Scan, OS Fingerprint, Brute Force SSH, Botnet ARES, and two DoS attacks (Slowloris and Goldeneye).

Performance metrics, including I/O metrics, CPU and RAM usage, were monitored using “mpstat -p ALL 1” and “htop,” respectively. Moreover, for the I/O Metrics the “iostat 2” command was executed. Wireshark was used on both VMs to capture transmitted and received packets. CPU and RAM usage was sampled every second, with averages and standard deviations calculated for each scenario.

A. Experiment Scenarios

The evaluation aimed to compare three scenarios to identify the least resource-intensive and most efficient solution for preventing cyber-attacks. Snort, a popular NIDS/NIPS, was chosen for its ability to integrate ML, while DT, a recent literature-based approach, was selected for its alternative methodology. The third scenario involved eIDPS, the proposed eBPF and XDP-based solution with an ML model for real-time detection and prevention at the NIC driver level. Comparing user-space (Snort) and kernel-based (DT, eIDPS) solutions highlighted differences in speed and resource usage.

In the first scenario, Snort was configured with custom rules and an ML plugin to drop malicious packets based on the CICIDS2017 dataset. However, operating in user space introduced latency. The second scenario used DT, originally a NIDS, modified to include packet prevention capabilities using eBPF. The third scenario deployed eIDPS, combining eBPF, XDP, and an ML model for real-time detection and prevention at the kernel level.

The evaluation occurred in two levels: first, comparing Snort (user-space) and eIDPS (kernel-based) using the same

ML model; second, comparing eIDPS (with a neural network model) to DT (with a decision tree model), which was modified to include XDP for packet dropping. Both levels used the CICIDS2017 dataset for ML model training.

B. Basis of comparison and Validity of Results

This study acknowledges the inherent differences between the evaluated solutions, particularly in their operational layers and underlying ML models. However, despite these variations, the comparative evaluation remains valid in assessing the potential of eIDPS. By structuring the evaluation across multiple levels, first comparing eIDPS with Snort to isolate the impact of kernel-based processing and then to DT to assess the effect of different ML models, this study ensures a balanced assessment. Although architectural differences introduce certain biases, they also reflect real-world trade-offs between user-space and kernel-based security mechanisms. Therefore, the results provide meaningful information on the efficiency and practicality of eIDPS, demonstrating its advantages in real-time intrusion detection and prevention while highlighting areas for future optimization and research.

C. Machine Learning training and validation Pre-configuration metrics

The accuracy, precision, recall and F1-score of an ML model are the the metrics selected for comparison of the ML models. Table I summarizes the performance metrics of the selected model, after it was tested on a testing dataset. More specifically, the accuracy, which is the ratio of correctly predicted observations to the total observations, was at 98.3% while the recall, which is the ratio of correctly predicted positive observations to all the observations in the actual class, was 98.0%. Moreover, the precision, which is the ratio of correctly predicted positive observations to the total predicted positives, was 98.2%, and the F1-score, the harmonic mean of precision and recall, was at 98.0%.

On the other hand, in the DT scenario a Decision Tree was utilized, as per the initial proposal of this solution in the literature, that was also trained with the CICIDS-2017 dataset resulting in a 94.5% accuracy, 97.8% F1-score, 96.3% recall and 97.6% precision on the testing dataset after training.

TABLE I: Overall metrics

	Neural Network	Decision Tree
Overall Precision	0.982	0.976
Overall Recall	0.980	0.963
Overall F1-score	0.980	0.978
Overall Accuracy	0.983	0.945

Table II compares the performance metrics of the two ML models, NN and DT for each attack. The table provides insights in recall, precision, and F1-score of both models for each class. For the Botnet attack the NN significantly outperforms the DT with a recall of 0.989, precision of 99.3%, and F1-score of 96.8%, compared to the DT’s recall of 80.1%, precision of 82.6%, and F1-score of 81.3%. Furthermore, in benign traffic the NN model performed better in terms of recall (97.9% vs. 95.6%), precision (99.6% vs. 96.7%), and

F1-score (98.7% vs. 93.6%) compared to the DT. In summary, these metrics are crucial for evaluating the effectiveness of the models in correctly classifying instances of each class and show that the NN has the upper hand.

TABLE II: Metrics for each attack

Class	Neural Network			Decision Tree		
	Recall	Precision	F1-score	Recall	Precision	F1-score
Benign	97.9%	99.6%	98.7%	95.6%	96.7%	93.6%
Botnet	0.989	0.993	0.968	0.801	82.6%	81.3%
DDoS	98.7%	99.8%	99.2%	99.3%	98.1%	97.2%
DoS GoldenEye	95.1%	98.8%	96.9%	92.9%	97.8%	98.4%
DoS Hulk	99.9%	94.6%	97.1%	99.7%	94.3%	97.5%
DoS Slowhttptest	97.0%	97.0%	97.0%	99.0%	98.0%	98.0%
DoS slowloris	87.9%	98.2%	92.7%	83.9%	99.9%	98.3%
FTP-Patator	99.3%	99.7%	99.5%	99.1%	98.3%	95.8%
PortScan	99.7%	82.8%	90.5%	93.7%	94.6%	91.2%
SSH-Patator	90.9%	98.5%	94.6%	93.1%	96.4%	95.7%

D. Results

1) *CPU and RAM usage*: According to [20], precisely measuring the system’s resources in eBPF scenarios, such as in the eIDPS and DT scenarios evaluated in this study, is challenging due to the operation of eBPF in the kernel and direct packet filtering in the NIC’s driver. Therefore, it is not possible to quantify the CPU and RAM use of packet filtering when it is executed directly in the kernel, as it operates at a highly granular level. An approach to address this problem is to ascertain the total amount of resources that the entire kernel utilizes during the cyber-attacks. Based on these indicators, one can only approximate the proportion of system resources that are utilized during the eIDPS and DT scenarios, keeping under consideration that the CPU utilization in both situations is actually lower than the percentage utilized by the kernel. This is because the eIDPS and DT are integrated inside the kernel and only consume a portion of the CPU percentage attributed to the entire kernel.

The cyber-attacks that were launched during all the scenarios are depicted alongside with the CPU and RAM Usage during each attack in Figure 4 and Figure 5.

Fig. 4: CPU usage

In the first evaluation level, Snort exhibited high CPU consumption, reaching 18.70% and 19.27% during OS Fingerprinting and Botnet attacks, respectively, while eIDPS maintained significantly lower usage at 1.55% and 1.43%. Similar trends were observed across other attacks, including Brute Force, Slowloris, Goldeneye, and SYN Scan.

In the second evaluation level, DT showed CPU usage of 1.89% and 1.82% for OS Fingerprinting and Botnet attacks, whereas eIDPS remained slightly lower at 1.55% and 1.43%. The small yet consistent difference arises from DT’s reliance on conditional checks, which disrupt CPU branch prediction, whereas eIDPS’s neural network executes more predictable mathematical operations, optimizing CPU efficiency.

Overall, DT and eIDPS significantly outperformed Snort due to their kernel-level operation. The slight advantage of eIDPS over DT, though modest, enhances scalability and efficiency, making it particularly valuable in resource-constrained or high-traffic environments. Even minor CPU savings can contribute to system stability and performance in large-scale deployments.

The RAM usage evaluation compares the efficiency of eIDPS, DT, and Snort across various attack scenarios. This analysis highlights the resource consumption of each system, emphasizing the advantages of eBPF and XDP in reducing memory overhead during real-time intrusion detection and prevention.

Fig. 5: RAM usage

In the first evaluation level, Snort exhibited high RAM consumption, reaching 6.65% and 7.00% during the Slowloris and Botnet attacks, respectively, whereas eIDPS maintained significantly lower usage at 0.42% and 0.45%. Similar trends were observed across other attacks, emphasizing Snort’s resource-intensive nature due to its user-space operation, compared to eIDPS’s efficient kernel-level processing with eBPF and XDP.

In the second evaluation level, DT showed RAM usage of 0.68% and 0.73% for the Goldeneye and OS Fingerprinting attacks, while eIDPS demonstrated slightly lower usage at 0.36% and 0.39%. Although the differences between DT and eIDPS were modest, they highlight eIDPS’s enhanced optimization for real-time intrusion detection and prevention.

Overall, both DT and eIDPS significantly outperformed Snort in memory efficiency. The reduced RAM consumption of eIDPS makes it better suited for high-traffic environments or resource-constrained deployments, ensuring scalability and consistent performance.

2) *Packets received*: In order to assess the effectiveness of the three systems the packets that were transmitted and received as well as the packets passed into the system were captured in all scenarios in real-time. These numbers of packets are plotted in Figure 6 for Snort, DT and eIDPS

scenarios. To evaluate the effectiveness of the three systems, the number of transmitted, received, and processed packets was recorded in real-time, as depicted in Figure 6.

Fig. 6: Packets received

In the first evaluation level, Snort underperformed compared to eIDPS, receiving 929 out of 1600 transmitted packets during the SYN scan attack and 1139 out of 2000 during the Brute Force attack, whereas eIDPS received only 281 and 100 packets, respectively. In the second level of evaluation, DT demonstrated better efficiency than Snort but remained less effective than eIDPS, letting through 426 and 329 packets in the same scenarios. Similar trends were observed for other cyber-attacks, with eIDPS consistently filtering more malicious packets.

Additionally, DoS attack experiments (Goldeneye and Slowloris) were conducted to assess system resilience. Snort struggled to manage these threats effectively, as its generic detection approach failed to address protocol-level vulnerabilities. In contrast, DT and eIDPS demonstrated superior mitigation capabilities. DT let through 600 and 527 packets during the Slowloris and Goldeneye attacks, while eIDPS allowed only 199 and 200 packets, respectively.

Overall, eIDPS outperformed both Snort and DT in CPU and RAM efficiency, as well as in blocking malicious packets.

3) *Latency*: Latency refers to the time between a packet's arrival and its filtering or forwarding, which is crucial for network performance. Lower latency enables faster processing and timely threat mitigation. eBPF-based solutions, particularly eIDPS, exhibit the lowest latency, averaging around 20ns per packet, while DT has a slightly higher latency of 50ns per packet. In contrast, Snort, a userspace solution, has a significantly higher latency, averaging 120ns per packet, reflecting slower processing typical of userspace systems.

4) *Input/Output Metrics*: In the Snort, DT, and eIDPS scenarios, I/O metrics were recorded alongside CPU usage and packet counts, including transactions per second (tps), read/write throughput (KB_read/s, KB_wrtn/s), and discarded data (KB_dscd/s). While attacks did not trigger significant disk reads, these metrics establish a baseline, confirming that system resources like CPU and network bandwidth, rather than storage, were the primary attack targets.

In the first evaluation, Snort recorded 2 transactions and 540 KB total writes during the Goldeneye attack, while eIDPS had

TABLE III: I/O Metrics

Cyber-attacks	tps			KB_wrtn/s			KB_wrtn		
	eIDPS	Snort	DT	eIDPS	Snort	DT	eIDPS	Snort	DT
OS Fingerprint	2	3	2	12	34	14	24	68	26
Botnet ARES	2.5	3	2.5	24	270	28	52	124	54
SYN Scan	2.5	3	2.5	26	62	28	52	124	54
Slowloris	2	3.5	2	26	200	28	52	400	56
Goldeneye	2.5	3	2.5	24	320	32	48	640	64
Brute Force SSH	2.5	3	2.5	26	270	26	52	540	54

2.5 transactions and 52 KB total writes, with similar trends across other attacks. In the second evaluation, DT performed nearly as efficiently as eIDPS, writing 64 KB versus 48 KB during Goldeneye, with comparable results in other attacks. Overall, eIDPS and DT showed minimal I/O impact, with eIDPS slightly outperforming DT, while Snort was the least efficient.

E. Discussion

The experimental results confirm that the proposed eIDPS solution efficiently detects and mitigates cyber-attacks while consuming minimal system resources. By leveraging kernel-level processing, eIDPS delegates packet handling to the NIC driver, and enhancing processing speed. Furthermore, the use of kernel buffers for packet storage significantly contributed to the smaller amount of I/O transactions occurrences during the cyber-attacks.

ML integration played a key role in packet classification, with eIDPS outperforming DT in rejection efficiency, likely due to the greater predictive power of neural networks. Snort, despite using the same ML model and dataset, was less effective due to its user-space processing, leading to higher CPU utilization, a larger number of I/O transactions and reduced attack detection capability.

The differences between DT and eIDPS, as seen in Figures 4 5 and Table II, stem from their distinct eBPF implementations. eIDPS integrates a neural network with optimized real-time packet filtering, while DT follows a different ML approach. These design choices impact runtime performance, with Figures 4 5 highlighting eIDPS's superior efficiency in CPU usage and RAM usage and I/O metrics shown in III, whereas Table II focuses on classification metrics. Ultimately, eIDPS's streamlined eBPF program minimizes overhead, making it the most effective solution.

V. CONCLUSION

Nowadays, software applications that safeguard computer network systems are essential, due to the significant and escalating risk of cyber-attacks. eBPF is a novel technology that has already seen great growth and in the future it is argued that it could be the go-to solution not only for cyber-security, but also for system monitoring. Similarly, ML is subject to continuous evolution and its integration into cyber-security solutions has emerged during the past years. Taking into consideration the aforementioned factors, this study presented a novel approach that offers a lightweight and effective solution for network intrusion detection and prevention combining eBPF with ML.

The proposed proof-of-concept eIDPS solution showcased great efficiency in detecting and dropping malicious packets during cyber-attacks, while utilizing a limited amount of system resources, surpassing the capabilities of current intrusion detection and prevention solutions.

A. Limitations

The proposed eBPF-based solution has inherent constraints, including a one-million-line code limit, restrictions on unbounded loops and memory relocation, and the absence of floating-point arithmetic support. Moreover, since the evaluation was conducted in a controlled environment without external interference, real-world testing is essential for further validation.

B. Future Work

Future work could focus on enhancing eBPF and the Linux kernel to improve traffic handling and detection capabilities. Additionally, benchmarking against similar systems would provide a more comprehensive evaluation of the proposed solution. A security analysis could also be conducted to identify potential vulnerabilities and strengthen system resilience.

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